

SPECIFIC PRINCIPLES AND METHODS OF TEACHING THE NATIONAL WRESTLING SPORT TO THE YOUNG GENERATION

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ABSTRACT

In this topic, the author stated that wrestling, which is currently our national sport, should be fully taught and developed to the next generation, as well as include this sport in the program of the OLYMPIC Games.

National wrestling training is a year-round pedagogical process of sports improvement aimed at achieving high sports results of the young generation. The purpose of the national wrestling training is to achieve maximum possible technical-tactical, physical and mental training for this athlete and to show high results in the competition. The main tasks to be solved during the training are as follows:

- thorough mastering of fighting techniques and tactics;
- to ensure the development of movement qualities to the necessary extent, to increase the functional capabilities of the participants and to strengthen their health;
- education of moral and will qualities;
- development of various aspects of the athlete's training and showing it in the activity of the competition;
- acquisition of theoretical knowledge and practical experience necessary for successful training and competition activities.

Training tasks are performed together. However, depending on the period and stages of training, the training of the wrestler, his skill level and other factors, more attention is paid to one task and less to another. Each task of the training is solved sequentially, that is, in the conditions of a gradual increase in the requirements for the participants.

The principles of teaching in the national struggle: In modern pedagogy, the principles of teaching are understood as basic requirements and guiding rules that determine the nature of the teacher's activity and the student's cognitive activity. Practical pedagogical activity is based on the principles of teaching, which serve as a guide for planning, organizing and analyzing teaching practice.

The training process in national wrestling is conducted in accordance with the main principles of physical education: educational nature, comprehensive development, health and practical importance.

The educational feature of teaching is the legitimacy of the educational process. Here, along with the growth of sports skills of wrestlers, personal moral standards are formed. Preparation and education of the sports reserve is related to solving a number of complex educational problems. In order to achieve high results in sports, it is of great importance to train the skills of self-control, analysis and evaluation of technical and tactical actions in wrestlers. All this is the result of the educational influence of the coach, under his leadership, the participants get the experience of being ready to solve life situations. In addition to professional skills, a coach must be highly moral and cultured, conscientiously approach his responsibilities, be truthful, and love and care for children. The manifestation of these qualities in the coach's personality determines the effectiveness of the educational process.

The principle of all-round development directs the coach to form a well-developed athlete's personality. Sports activities are closely related to spiritual, mental, labor, aesthetic and other types of education. Achieving the goals set at different stages of training, striving to overcome difficulties forms spiritual experience, qualities of will, independent thinking, hard work, perseverance in sports victories and defeats.

The healthy direction of the national wrestling training is the growth of sports skills and the strengthening of health, physical development, musculoskeletal system, cardiovascular, respiratory and nervous system of the participants. expressed through Failure to follow this principle, especially at the initial stages of sports training, leads to regular, and in some cases, chronic illness in teenage wrestlers and is the main reason why athletes with mass discharge do not engage in wrestling.

The practical direction is of great practical importance in this national struggle. The practical manifestation of this principle implies that a wrestler should be able to act in unexpected situations. Senior athletes need to be able to protect themselves and their loved ones. The successful conduct of wrestling training is determined by compliance with the main pedagogical principles of this process. The effectiveness of training is based on the following didactic principles:

1. The scientific principle of teaching.
2. The principle of ease of teaching.
3. The principle of regularity of teaching.
4. The principle of awareness and activity of teaching.
5. The principle of demonstration of teaching.
6. The principle of thorough assimilation of educational material.
7. The principle of unity of team teaching and individual approach to the student.
8. The principle of connection between teaching and practice.
9. The importance of the teacher's leadership in the teaching process.

The methods of using the word used by the teacher activate the entire learning process, help to form more complete and clear ideas about movements. With the help of these methods, the teacher analyzes and evaluates learning material.

Visual perception methods ensure that the studied actions are perceived by sight and hearing. Visual reception helps to acquire actions more quickly, deeply and firmly, arouses interest in the studied actions.

Practical methods are based on the active movement of the participants. They are conditionally divided into two groups: strictly and partially ordered exercise styles, forms of movement, load sizes, its growth, alternating with rest, and many repetitions of movements with strict ordering of others characterized by As a result, it is possible to gradually form the necessary movements and master individual movements.

The method of learning in parts involves first learning individual parts of the movement, and then combining them as a whole as needed.

A holistic approach to learning is based on the ultimate goal of learning, and involves learning the action as it is.

The method of partially ordered exercises allows students to choose actions relatively freely to solve the tasks set before them.

The style of the game is characterized by the strict ordering of actions, the absence of possible conditions for their execution; creates ample opportunities for independent manifestation of creative abilities, ensures that training takes place in an upbeat spirit.

Competition style refers to specially organized competition activities. In this case, this activity is used as a method of increasing the effectiveness of training sessions.

Conclusion: Thus, in the training sessions, all the listed methods are used in various combinations, not in standard forms, but in modified forms, taking into account the specific requirements of sports training. When choosing styles, it is necessary to pay attention to the fact that they must be strictly consistent with the set tasks, general didactic principles, as well as special principles of sports training, age characteristics of the participants, their qualifications and level of training.

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